

ASSOCIATION BETWEEN LIPID PEROXIDATION ACTIVITY AND
HYPERENZYMIA IN CHRONIC HEPATITIS C

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Relevance

Any pathological process, including chronic hepatitis C, is accompanied by increased production of free radicals and subsequent activation of lipid peroxidation processes. These changes lead to alterations in the structural and functional properties of biological membranes and contribute to cellular dysfunction. The primary protective role against excessive lipid peroxidation is performed by the cellular antioxidant system. Insufficiency of this system becomes one of the key factors promoting prooxidant reactions in the body. Therefore, studying lipid peroxidation processes in chronic hepatitis C and their relationship with disease activity remains an important scientific and clinical task.

Objective

To investigate the state of lipid peroxidation processes and their association with the activity of the pathological process in patients with chronic hepatitis C.

Materials and Methods

The study included 47 patients with chronic hepatitis C aged 20 to 50 years and 10 practically healthy individuals without markers of viral hepatitis who served as the control group.

The clinical diagnosis was established based on medical history, clinical and laboratory findings, and the detection of anti-HCV antibodies (ELISA) and HCV RNA (PCR). According to the recommendations of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan Order No. 5 dated January 5, 2012, the degree of pathological activity was assessed based on the severity of cytolytic syndrome and serum levels of alanine aminotransferase (ALT) and aspartate aminotransferase (AST): minimal activity (1.5–2 times above normal), low activity (2–3 times), moderate activity (3–5 times), and high activity (more than 5 times above normal). Lipid peroxidation and prooxidant system activity were evaluated by measuring primary products—diene ketones and diene conjugates—as well as the secondary product malondialdehyde (MDA). Statistical analysis was performed using the Statistica software package with Student's t-test.

Results

Analysis of the obtained data demonstrated that none of the examined patients had cytolysis indicators exceeding five times the normal values. Only minimal (20 patients), low (17 patients), and moderate (10 patients) degrees of pathological activity were identified. In all examined patients, activation of the prooxidant system was observed.

Compared with the control group, significantly higher levels of primary lipid peroxidation products were detected, including diene ketones (0.32 ± 0.03 vs. 0.67 ± 0.06 units/ml) and diene conjugates (1.07 ± 0.06 vs. 1.86 ± 0.12 units/ml), as well as the secondary product MDA (2.50 ± 0.05 vs. 3.76 ± 0.44 nmol/l). No statistically significant differences in these indicators were found among patient groups with different degrees of pathological activity.

Conclusion

Patients with chronic hepatitis C demonstrate increased levels of both primary and secondary lipid peroxidation products, including diene ketones, diene conjugates, and malondialdehyde. At the same time, no clear association between lipid peroxidation intensity and the degree of pathological activity was identified, indicating that oxidative stress activation occurs regardless of disease activity level.

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